

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 11

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DEXTER O. BUTEL

Instructor I

Apayao State College

dexytel022897@gmail.com

“ASHES ON HIS SHOULDER”

Existence is a precious offering, given to all. There is nothing more beautiful than living a life where nothing is made to feel out of place. Many people often perceive small things as worthless. They do not give it much attention because, for them, it is a mere scratch. Perhaps, their small stature causes others to underestimate their full potential. Even worse is the notion that a minute is provisional, meant to pass quickly. But the irony is, those things that they frequently classify as invaluable are what they enjoy the most. Little do everybody know that everything starts from scratch. All things seen big were only a dot yesterday.

In a small town of a province, as late afternoon settles in, wisps of smoke can be seen rising into the air while people are wandering around. At first glance, all seems beautiful and fair. It is more like a place untouched by feelings of contempt. The place also appears prosperous, as most people residing there have extraordinary skills for business. It is, therefore, unsurprising that sales booths are seen positioned in every corner, as managing their own business has been their primary means of subsistence. Some are selling branded apparel, cosmetics, and fancy food and beverages. These businesses are high-end. However, in the deepest nook, far from the madding crowd, there is this young man whose business is far simpler than others. It may come off as a tiny business, but it is often flocked with customers in the afternoon.

Denxio is a 22-year-old humble man, whose only wish is to pull his family out from the quagmire of poverty. Although his family is regarded as indigent, he managed to graduate from college with a Bachelor of Science in Business Administration. During his study journey, he invested nothing but perseverance and hard work. Right after his graduation, Denxio decided to indulge himself in a venture aligned with his finished degree. He is the owner of the small business in town, investing five hundred pesos of his savings as revolving capital. He invented his signature recipe for the goods he sells, maintained sanitary practices, and treated customers with utmost respect. Denxio adhered to a perceived fundamental business operational approach gained from his studies. The business gradually flourishes each day. His persistence in meeting the demands of the customers makes his business always packed. Until nearby businesses began to hate him out of resentment.

Malicious envy is commonly viewed as among the root causes of cutthroat competition in the business environment. A supposed endeavor to gain competitive advantage without engaging to any damaging or illegal practices has totally changed and contravened. Hence, the chance for some businesses to prosper and the goal they also wish to achieve are compromised. It is a dog-eat-dog world where Denxio faced extreme embarrassment and several baseless accusations. Nevertheless, it did not stop him from continuing his passion. He still kept selling in the succeeding days, but it was no longer busy like it used to be. At the lowest point of his journey, someone approached him and offered help.

"Hello! Denxio. I feel so bad for everything that happened to you. I may be a stranger, but I am actually here to help you.", Lexy proposed to him.

Denxio could not do anything anymore but to accept the proposal. Eventually, they became business partners. The partnership went well and things gradually returned to normal. Denxio was grateful as he noticed progress of their business, as if there are no more problems coming. In an unlooked-for situation, a rumor went around town. Someone got food poisoning. The people were blaming no one else but Denxio. He was distressed at that time and vehemently denied the accusation.

"She had never bought anything from me!", Denxio insisted. Suddenly, he heard a resounding voice from a close distance like a deafening thunder to his ears along with speaking words, "She did!".

When he tried to lift his head, he saw Lucy, his business partner. The police conducted investigation but found no strong evidence to convict Denxio of the crime. Due to what happened, Denxio has also decided to close the business, having learned that not all visible to the eye is real, nor is all help is a form of kindness. Trusting others is not bad, but someone should trust himself above all else.

A year later, the issue had permanently subsided and he was completely exonerated. The trust in him had been restored. It was the town's annual celebration, and a business exposition was one of the highlights. Everyone with business potential was invited.

"Denxio, you should join the business exposition. We are sure you'll going to make it!", hid friends urged."

"Do you think I can do it? All I have is simple.", Denxio replied.

The day has come. All business owners from the town joined the competition and Denxio was one of the contenders. He was busy preparing for his presentation when someone drew near to him.

'Long time no see, Denxio. Good thing you still have the courage to return with your cheap business!', His former business partner, Lucy, sarcastically told him."

Denxio remained silent and continued with the work he was doing.

The presentation has arrived, and it is time for Denxio to take over. When he attempted to speak, someone called his attention and tried to humiliate him.

"Have at least a bit of decency, Denxio. Ashes on your shoulder? That was quite ridiculous," a familiar voice came from the audience and it was Lucy.

When he almost decided not to continue anymore, a master chef which happened to be the chairman of the judges called his attention.

"You'll never reach your long-wished destination if you allow others' validation to hold you back. As long as you're not doing anything wrong, there is nothing to be afraid or ashamed regarding the thing you're passionate about.", he conveyed to Denxio.

After hearing those stirring words, Denxio began to speak.

"Warm greetings and a pleasant day to all. You may regard my business as small and humble compared to others, but it is nurtured with love and passion. The Ashes on My Shoulder embodies every inch of my invested time and energy,

grilling a unique and lasting brand identity for my Barbeque entity. It is capable of bringing delight and a momentary escape from a repetitive and distressing reality. My goal goes beyond mere profit. It is to provide customers with joy and a worthwhile experience.", sincerely shared by Denxio."

After he finished his pitch, the crowd and all the judges went wild. They gave to Denxio the warmest and loudest appreciation. It was one of his most remarkable moments.

Another year has passed after the notable business exposition, and Denxio has finally stopped selling barbeque. There were no longer any wisps of smoke rising into the air made by him as late afternoon settled in. The place where he used to sell was already occupied by another business owner.

It was that time of year again, the town's annual celebration. As expected, a business exposition is about to begin. Many business owners have again joined the activity, but nobody among the contenders named Denxio was included that time. The contenders have presented their master pieces well, except for one. A girl named Dixie was diffident to present her products, for she allegedly only had banana fritters. When suddenly a man started speaking to her,

"You should not have any reason to be ashamed. There is nothing wrong with what you have. Even the things started from scratch are the most invaluable and capable ones of reaching heights.", an inspiring message that helped the girl win the competition, came from the chairman of the board of judges, a high-caliber-looking man named Denxio.

Denxio was then working for one of the country's largest business consulting companies as a senior business consultant. He continued to deliver community business-related programs to business owners, helping many businesses to prosper. His family also maintained a modest lifestyle.

The small things are often the ones that go unnoticed. They are considered to have no value. Perhaps, the standard of what is truly big and valuable for others is based on beauty and cost. In the absence of sufficient power, the small ones continue to be betrayed and destroyed by the greedy big ones. They may be only very tiny particles for now, like the seeds in the garden, but they will surely bloom later like beautiful flowers that add beauty and meaning to the world. At the end of the day, it has nothing to do with whether something is big or small. Each has its own unique potential and value.

